

Metal Complexes II: Electrical Properties of the Transition Metal Complexes of 6-Mercaptopurine and 4-Mercapto-6,7-diphenyl-pteridine¹

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The semiconductive properties of selected transition metal complexes of 6-Mercaptopurine and of 4-Mercapto-6,7-diphenylpteridine were studied and are discussed.

Investigations of semiconduction in organic systems started on the basis of the original suggestion of Szent Gyorgyi that, in the organic macromolecular systems, the energy transfer process might be analogous to semiconduction in crystals, and that the regular arrangement in the molecule could result in bands of energy similar to those in inorganic semiconductors⁴. Since then the photo- and semiconductive properties of various organic systems including the metal complexes of phthalocyanine and natural metal complexes such as haemoglobin and chlorophyll have been reported⁵. However, the metal-organic complexes derived from simple ligands have so far received very little attention. The earlier investigations of Eley, and of Kanda and Kawaguchi of the copper complexes of glycine⁶, 1, 6-dihydroxyphenazine, 2, 5-dihydroxy p-benzoquinone, and tubeanic acid⁷ are amongst the few such studies reported. Recently Dewar has suggested that efficient energy transfer in ligand-metal complexes could be expected, provided that the complexes are of cholate type with through-conjugation and that they have square-planar or octahedral structure. This view was supported by the evaluation of the semiconductive properties of polymeric transition metal complexes of the oxime of 1,5-diacetyl-2, 6-dihydroxy naphthalene⁸.

As part of a program of study of organic semi- and photoconductors we have been engaged in the evaluation of the electrical properties of stable metal complexes involving heterocyclic ligands. In view of the recent publication on the photo- and semiconductive-properties of selected purines and pyrimidine bases of biological interest by Basu⁹ we like to report the semiconductive properties of selected transition metal complexes of 6-mer-

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captapurino (6-MP) and 4-mercapto-6, 7-diphenyl-pteridine (4-SHPT). The selection of these ligands was based on their ability to form solid complexes, and only these complexes which show reproducible analytical and electrical properties are reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

The metal complexes were prepared from the purified ligands and the corresponding transition metal salts in aqueous dioxane¹⁰. The precipitated complexes were washed and dried in vacuum for several hours. The specific resistivity (ρ) of the complexes was measured in sandwich-type cells as pressed pellets, or as sedimentation layers on "Pyrex" or "Vycor" conductive glass plates (thickness—0.55 to 1.0 mm, area 3 cm²) after drying at 110°, at a potential in the range 180-225 volts. The temperature dependence of resistivity was measured in a temperature-controlled oven between 300 to 353°K. The dark current (i) was measured using a Keithly 610A electrometer. The ultraviolet and visible spectra were determined either in solution, or in KBr pellets using a Cary-14 spectrophotometer. The I.R. spectra was obtained in KBr pellets, using a P.E. Infracord of P.E.-221 Spectrophotometer.

Table I presents the calculated specific resistivities of the ligands and of the complexes at 300°K. The activation energy was obtained from the slope of the plots based on the relation $\log i = \log i_0 E_a / K_r$. In each case a straight line was obtained (Fig. 1). The specific resistivity of the complexes of a given sample in different cells was not found to vary more than one-half an order of magnitude.

TABLE I

Electrical Properties of 6-Mercaptopurine and 4-Mercapto-6,7-diphenylpteridine complexes

Compound	T°K	E _a (ev)	ρ ohm Cm (300°K)	ρ_0 ohm Cm
6-Mercaptopurine	310-356	0.652	1.97×10^{16}	2.57×10^8
Bis-6-Mercaptopurine Co (11)- Monohydrate	300-354	0.497	9.17×10^{14}	4.28×10^6
Bis-6-Mercaptopurine-Ni (11) Dihydrate	308-348.5	0.477	7.0×10^{13}	6.69×10^5
Tris-6-Mercaptopurine- Cd (11) Pentahydrate	300-356	0.711	8.65×10^{13}	1.09×10^6
4-Mercapto-6, 7-diphenylpteridine	300-350	0.675	7.95×10^{15}	9.5×10^8
4-Mercapto-6, 7-diphenylpteridine- Cu(11) dihydrate	300-350	0.695	5.86×10^{13}	4.76×10^6
Bis-4-Mercapto-6, 7-diphenyl- pteridine Co (11)-pentahydrate	309-350	0.352	5.86×10^{15}	7.03×10^{10}

DISCUSSION

The specific resistivity of an intrinsic semiconductor is given as a function of the temperature by the equation,

$$\log \rho = \log \rho_0 + E_a/KT$$

where K is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, ρ_0 , a constant which provides a measure of carrier mobility and E_a is the activation energy of conduction which is related to energy gap (E_g) between filled and conduction bands ($E_a = 1/2 E_g$). The specific resistivities of the complexes in most cases are appreciably different from those of the ligands. However, the resistivities of the complexes are, as expected much higher than those of the polymeric metal complexes^{7, 8}. The activation energies of the present complexes are fairly close to those of the ligands 6-MP and 4-SHPT and of the polymeric complexes⁸.

FIG. 1 Temperature dependence of resistivity of metal complexes.

Attempts have been made to identify the molecular energy state (measured as optical transition energies), (ΔE) of intrinsic semiconductors with the energy gap E_g ^{3b}, Kuroda¹¹ has shown that for 1:1 tetracyanoethylene-hydrocarbon- π -complex, the charge-transfer energies (ΔE_{ct}) approximately match the energy gaps, E_g .

The transition energies (ΔE) corresponding to the onset of absorption in the infrared region for the complexes studied by Dewar⁸ were also found to be of the same order of magnitude as E_g . The insoluble Co, Ni and Cd, 6-MP complexes show broad absorption bands in the visible and the transition energies associated with the onset of absorption in the 2.0 to 2.5 μ region (0.62 to 0.50 eV) in the infrared in most cases are within the range of the E_g values. The 4-SHPT-Cu (11) complex, however, shows besides the

principal absorption band of the ligand-metal conjugated structure (556 m μ); a low intensity band at 960 m μ (1.29 ev) which corresponds with the E_g values of 1.3 ev.

These observations lead us to conclude that the metal complexes constitute intrinsic semiconductors. The detailed nature of the conduction process, i.e., the relative contributions made by the ligand and by the water remains to be elucidated. The possible role of adventitious impurities must, of course, also be borne in mind.

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